

In hoeverre wil jij
kunstmatige intelligentie
in het dagelijks leven
gebruiken?

Translation: To what extent do you want to use artificial intelligence in everyday life? Let your voice be heard!

Op welke manieren kunnen
we kunstmatige intelligentie
gebruiken, terwijl we
onze menselijke
waarden behouden?

Translation: in what ways can we use artificial intelligence
while maintaining our human values?
Let your voice be heard!

Hoe zie je de **rol**
van **kunstmatige intelligentie**
in het **creatieve** proces
van **kunst** maken?

Laat je
stem horen!

Translation: how do you see the role of artificial intelligence
in the creative process of making art?

Let your voice be heard!

**Welke taken kan en mag
kunstmatige intelligentie
van mensen overnemen?**

**Laat je
stem horen!**

Translation: what tasks can and should artificial intelligence take over from humans? Let your voice be heard!

Is kunstmatige intelligentie
altijd een positieve toevoeging?
Of zijn er volgens jou ook risico's?

Laat je
stem horen!

Translation: is artificial intelligence always a positive addition? Or do you think there are also risks?

Let your voice be heard!

Hier kun je je mening over kunstmatige intelligentie op een post-it schrijven en op het prikbord hangen.
Laat je stem horen!

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Here you can write your opinion on artificial intelligence on
a post-it and hang it on the bulletin board.
Let your voice be heard!